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SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS THROUGH COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE IN A MANUFACTURING SECTOR: A CASE OF MANUFACTURING SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

Sustainability development is all about contributing to the country's economic development while not compromising the quality of the environment for future generations. The term stakeholder encompasses all individuals who are impacted by the company's products and services, not just those who have a financial stake in the company. As a result, it is critical for an organization to increase value in a sustainable manner.

OCCL has been in the insoluble sulphur business for nearly three decades. The company was founded on the concept of specialization in competencies, with the goal of remaining liquid and viable at the bottom of a market cycle. The quality standards required for the production of insoluble sulphur are constantly evolving, resulting in safer downstream products. Customers must wait years for vendors to be approved; thereafter, purchases are gradually scaled; and the quality derived from each successive capacity expansion must be approved by the customer. This places a premium on relationship engagement and stability, which serve as the foundation for growth in a demanding business.

OCCL manufactures products (or grades) that meet the needs of individual customers. Ensures environmental responsibility through products and processes and offers a variety of products, resulting in a one-stop solution. OCCL obtains the best resource quality through knowledge and relationships in order to sustain in the market and gain an advantage over competitors. Procure more economically through better trade terms, and procure more sustainably through multi-year relationships.

One of the most important aspects of a company is its employees, so the first responsibility of a company is to treat all employees equally and to ensure that the company provides an environment that aids in the overall development of the employees. At OCCL, there is an investment in knowledge, experience, and passion, which results in increased individual productivity.

As a business, it becomes the primary responsibility to protect the environment, which OCCL does by consuming fewer resources per unit of production and conducting business in accordance with current statutory and customer compliance standards.

Keywords: Sustainability, Pricing strategies, market competence.

INTRODUCTION

The processes and techniques used by firms to estimate the costs of their goods and services are known as pricing strategies. Your product pricing strategy is the method you use to decide what to charge for your items, if price is what you charge for them.

Pricing plans take into account a variety of organizational factors, including revenue targets, marketing objectives, target market, brand positioning, and product attributes. Additionally, they are impacted by outside variables like consumer demand, market and economic shifts, and competitive price.

The best pricing strategy maximizes your profit and revenue.

Let's go over an important pricing concept that applies to all pricing strategies.

Price Elasticity Of Demand

It is said that a product is inelastic if customers continue to purchase it in spite of a price increase (for instance, cigarettes and petrol).

$$\% \text{ Change in Quantity} \div \% \text{ Change in Price} = \text{Price Elasticity of Demand}$$

Objectives of Study:

- To understand the pricing strategies used in OCCL
- To create a pricing framework for various OCCL customers.

INDUSTRY AND COMPANY PROFILE

Insoluble sulphur is a preferred curing agent in the rubber industry, and is widely regarded as the best vulcanising agent. Tyres, rubber pipes, shoes, cable and wire insulating materials,

latex, and automobile rubber parts are all made with the product. However, the product's primary application is in the tyre industry.

Oriental Carbon & Chemicals Limited, founded in 1978, is a member of the JP Goenka Group of Companies. The company is a well-known manufacturer of insoluble sulphur. They have over 25 years of experience manufacturing this product. Over time, their expertise has translated into the ability to manufacture customized and value-added grades for our customers. These grades have assisted them in meeting the stringent requirements of some of the world's largest quality-driven tyre manufacturers. The company enjoys about 10% of the global market share and around 55–60% of the domestic market.

The Company is driven by a strong sense of customer service. Their service mindset is reflected in proactive investments in people, plant, and processes to deliver quality product. They are focused on providing interactive technical services to their clients. This capability has enabled them to provide comprehensive solutions to their customers.

Vision

To be present in every tyre of the world.

Mission

While striving to be present in every tyre of the world, we will:

For our people: Build trust and engagement by:

1. Creating success opportunities
2. Enabling a happy environment

For our customers: Build trust and reliability by:

1. Delivering quality
2. Optimizing costs

For our shareholders: Build trust and value by:

1. Delivering sustainable growth
2. Being socially responsible

MARKETING COMPETENCE

Strengths

Scale: The Company is among the largest insoluble sulphur manufacturers in the world, resulting in economies of scale (manufacturing, focused cost coverage and procurement).

Entry barrier: It is not easy for an insoluble sulphur manufacturer to get product approval from tyre companies and yet, the company's products have been approved by more than 40 customers worldwide.

Local: In an endeavor to provide local supplies/just-in-time deliveries and better services to global customers, the company has made arrangements for warehouses and partnered thirdparty logistics service providers.

Flexible: The Company is among handful manufacturers with flexible manufacturing facilities, helping deliver to clients required quantity and quality.

Value-added: The Company has been working collaboratively with tyre manufacturing companies to develop new value-added grades. OCCL added a new grade (DS Vulcamax) during the last financial year, aligned with evolving needs of the tyre industry.

PRODUCTS

The Company is one of a handful of global manufacturers of insoluble sulphur, a specialized raw material for tyres. The company also manufactures sulphuric acid and oleum in its Dharuhera unit.

➤ **Insoluble Sulphur**

“Diamond Sulf” is a polymeric form of sulphur, as opposed to natural sulphur, which is crystalline and monomeric. Diamond Sulf polymeric chains are made up of thousands of micro-fine sulphur particles. As long as the product is in polymeric form, it is insoluble in all known solvents and rubber compounds and does not participate in a cross-linking reaction like natural sulphur.

➤ **Sulphuric Acid**

The company manufactures commercial grade and battery grade sulphuric acid and oleums. The product finds application as a dehydrating agent, catalyst and active reactant in chemical processes, solvents and absorbents. It is also used in high purity grades in storage batteries, rayon, dye, acid slurry and pharmaceutical applications as well as commercial grades in the steel, heavy chemical and super-phosphate industries.

PRESENCE

OCCL markets products in more than 28 countries. Used by some of the largest and most demanding multi-national customers. Accounting for about 10% of the global production of insoluble sulphur.

The Company's insoluble sulphur product is marketed across the world through a multi-country distribution network comprising agents and distributors

Pricing Strategies followed In OCCL

Cost Oriented Pricing

It serves as the foundation for determining the cost of finished goods, and the majority of businesses use this method to determine product costs.

Market-Oriented Pricing

Market-based pricing is when a price of a product is set according to current market prices for the same or similar products. In other words, market-based pricing means setting prices in line with your competitors and products. Under this category, the price is determined on the basis of market research.

History-based Pricing

With cutting-edge analytical tools, pricing analytics can help brands track a wide range of pricing metrics and use insights to stay ahead of the competition. This study examines how previous pricing and promotion activities affect brand, sales, and customer price perception. It frequently entails identifying and exploiting opportunities and weaknesses in competitors' pricing strategies in order to increase sales and revenue.

In this case, the company looks at what price they offered the product to the customer in the past. It takes that price as the base price and adjusts the current price of the product accordingly.

Formula Pricing

Formula pricing is a crude or product pricing method in which a predetermined formula sets the price of the commodity relative to other benchmark crude or product prices, with little or no monthly input from the buyer or seller.

Pricing Framework

Every company has its own pricing framework and wants to accomplish different things with it. For example, one company may want to gain market share, another may be solely concerned with increasing profits, and yet another may want to be perceived as having prestige products. In OCCL, a lot of factors are taken into consideration while making a pricing framework, and it is done to see at what price they agreed to sell their product in the last quarter and what are the reasons that led an increase or decrease in their prices, whether it is due to a change in exchange rate, transportation cost, etc. It is made after every quarter because they do their business on a quarterly basis, and then the contribution is checked at the end of the year and compared with the last year, and then necessary changes are made in the pricing framework strategies to do better next year.

Some of the elements used in pricing framework are:

Budgeted Price: The Budget Price is the price specified in the Purchase Order for the works based on the Rate Schedule estimates.

Offered Price: In general, an offered price is the price at which something is offered for sale.

Agreed price: A mutually agreed-upon price is one on which both parties agree. The seller suggests a price to the customer, who then haggles a little. Finally, a price that benefits both parties is reached.

Exchange Rate: An exchange rate is the relative price of one currency in terms of another. Changes in it have an impact on economic activity, inflation, and the country's balance of payments.

Transportation cost: All costs associated with the transportation of raw materials, finished goods, and employees are included in transportation costs. It is the money spent to ensure that all moving parts get to where they need to go in order for your customers to receive their product or service on time.

Peer 2	Nokian Finland								
	Grade + Version								
	Agreed Price	EURO							
	Freight	USD							
	Freight	EURO							
	Loadability	Mt							
	Freight/MT	EURO							
	Commission								
	FOB	USD							
	FOB INR	INR							
	Cost of Production	INR							
	Contribution Margin (Rajesh's File)	INR							

The pricing framework of one customer is compared to the other customers to see what price the same grade was offered to the other customers and how much contribution the country received from each customer. In this manner, the pricing framework is created for each customer, and then a business insight report is created at the end to assess the overall contribution made by the company throughout the year, which is then compared to the previous year.

CONCLUSION

Pricing strategy is unavoidable; any organization must carefully plan its strategies before selling anything to its customers, whether it is a product or a service. Pricing strategy has the power to either make or break a company. A good pricing strategy takes into account a variety of variables such as market and economic changes, competitive pricing, and consumer demand.

Furthermore, this project helped me understand that no matter what the name or buzz about an organization is, the actual picture can be very different when numbers are involved.

Pricing strategy in a business is largely determined by the forecasting method and the use of various budgeting avenues.

This study also shows the strong relationship that exists between pricing strategy and overall firm performance. As a result, it can be concluded that carefully planned pricing strategies play a significant role in an organization's net profit.

REFERENCES

1. <https://www.profitwell.com/recur/all/pricing-strategy-guide/>
2. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/i/incoterms.asp>
3. <https://www.shippingsolutions.com/blog/shipping-documentation-process>
4. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/l/letterofcredit.asp>
5. <https://www2.deloitte.com/be/en/pages/strategy-operations/strategy-analytics-mergers-acquisitions/articles/pricing-framework.html>
6. <https://open.lib.umn.edu/principlesmarketing/chapter/15-1-the-pricing-framework-and-a-firms-pricing-objectives/>
7. <https://www.nynas.com/en/products/process-oils/applications/insoluble-sulphur/>